

EXERGY ANALYSIS OF THE PRODUCTION OF SELECTED CHEMICALS IN THE ENERGY TRANSITION SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT

Chemical reactants, mainly acids and bases – e.g. sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, sodium carbonate, and others – are a key part of mining and industrial processes. This means that their production – from a life-cycle perspective – plays a crucial role in the environmental impacts and exergy costs of the production of metals and other materials. In fact, up to 3 % of all global anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions can be traced back to the chemical industry. The production of chemicals consumes a large amount of energy, which is trying to be decarbonized. However, changing the energy from fossil fuels to electricity means that the chemical industry will be indirectly more dependent on metals, as renewable energy is more materials-intensive. The production of these metals, as explained before, is, in turn, dependent on chemicals. This situation poses a dynamic feedback loop whose effects propagate as the energy and electricity mix become greener and fossil fuels diminish their importance. In this work, we use a dynamic life-cycle assessment approach to study how different scenarios of the energy transition will affect the renewable and non-renewable exergy costs and environmental impacts of the two most used inorganic chemicals – sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide – and how these exergy costs affect the exergy costs of metals production. Furthermore, we discuss opportunities to achieve higher energy and exergy efficiencies. This work is part of the great model of the exergy analysis of the economy developed by our research group.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global demand for fundamental industrial chemicals such as sodium hydroxide (NaOH), also known as caustic soda, and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) underscores their vital role in numerous industrial processes and the broader economy. In 2023, the world market for sulphuric acid was greater than 260 million tons and is expected to grow up to 300 million tons by 2030 (Statista, 2024). Meanwhile, sodium hydroxide production the same year was 83 million tons and is expected to grow more than 3 % per year for the next decade (ChemAnalyst, 2023). Sodium hydroxide, predominantly produced through the energy-intensive chlor-alkali process involving brine electrolysis (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2017), serves as a crucial component in industries ranging from pulp and paper manufacturing to the production of soaps and detergents. Sulfuric acid, recognized as a high-volume commodity chemical, is essential in the production of fertilizers, petroleum refining, and the synthesis of a wide array of other chemicals and materials.

The chlor-alkali industry is a significant consumer of energy within the chemical sector. The electrolysis of brine to produce chlorine, sodium/potassium hydroxide, and hydrogen is inherently energy-intensive (Garcia-Herrero et al., 2017). Different technologies employed in the chlor-alkali process, including the now phasing-out mercury cell technology, the diaphragm cell technique, and the more energy-efficient membrane cell technique, exhibit varying energy consumption profiles (Brinkmann et al., 2014). Emerging technologies like the oxygen depolarised cathode (ODC), which replaces the hydrogen-evolving cathodes in membrane technology, offer the potential to reduce electricity consumption by

around 30% compared to standard membrane cell techniques. This modification works by reducing oxygen to produce hydroxide instead of converting water into hydrogen and hydroxyl ions.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has become an established methodology for evaluating the environmental impacts associated with a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life treatment (Lee & Inaba, 2004). Several studies have employed LCA to assess the sustainability of chlor-alkali and sulfuric acid production (Adeniran et al., 2017; Garcia-Herrero et al., 2017; Mami et al., 2018). These assessments can identify critical stages in the life cycle that contribute most significantly to environmental burdens, such as raw material acquisition, the production process itself, and waste treatment. For instance, in chlor-alkali production, the source and purification of brine (sodium chloride) and the energy consumed during electrolysis are key factors in its environmental footprint.

Similarly, the production of sulfuric acid, commonly achieved through the contact process involving the catalytic oxidation of sulfur dioxide (SO_2) to sulfur trioxide (SO_3), also entails considerable energy consumption and environmental emissions. LCA studies on sulfuric acid production have highlighted the significance of the elemental sulfur production stage and the energy consumed in the plant, including the production of demineralized water, as major contributors to its environmental impacts, such as acidification potential and abiotic depletion potential (Adeniran et al., 2017; Brunn et al., 1996).

Exergy analysis offers a complementary thermodynamic perspective to evaluate the quality of energy and the efficiency of processes by determining the maximum useful work obtainable from a system as it reaches equilibrium with its surroundings (Szargut et al., 1988). It allows for the identification of irreversibilities and losses of useful work, providing a more nuanced understanding of energy efficiency than first-law analysis alone (Kotas, 1987). The concept of exergy cost represents the cumulative exergy consumed to produce a good or service, reflecting the high-quality resource input required.

The integration of LCA and exergy analysis provides a robust framework for a more comprehensive sustainability assessment. While LCA quantifies a broad spectrum of environmental impacts, exergy analysis focuses on the efficiency of resource utilization from a thermodynamic standpoint. Analyzing the exergy cost within an LCA framework can reveal not only the environmental burdens but also the underlying thermodynamic inefficiencies throughout a product's life cycle. This is particularly relevant for energy-intensive processes like the production of sodium hydroxide and sulfuric acid, where minimizing exergy losses can lead to substantial environmental and economic benefits.

While LCA studies on the individual production of sodium hydroxide (Luis & Van der Bruggen, 2014) and sulfuric acid (Rasheva & Atanasova, 2002) exist, and exergy analysis has been increasingly applied to various industrial processes, there is a need for an integrated analysis that specifically evaluates the exergy costs of producing these two fundamental chemicals from a life-cycle perspective. This approach would enable a deeper understanding of the efficiency of high-quality resource use across their entire value chains, from raw material extraction to the plant gate ("cradle-to-gate"). Furthermore, in the context of the energy transition, the exergy cost of electricity is expected to vary in the future (Torrubia et al., 2024), which will have important implications in the exergy cost of the products. It must also be considered that the Energy Return On Investment (EROI) of fossil energies is decreasing, driving exergy costs up.

This article aims to analyze and compare the exergy costs associated with the production of sodium hydroxide and sulfuric acid using a Life Cycle Assessment framework. By examining the different life cycle stages, this study will identify critical points in terms of exergy consumption and discuss the implications for the sustainability of their production processes. Quantifying the exergy cost of these essential chemicals will provide valuable insights for decision-making aimed at improving resource efficiency and reducing the environmental impacts in the chemical sector. The analysis will consider the various chlor-alkali production technologies and the key stages in sulfuric acid production, exploring opportunities for thermodynamic optimization within a life cycle context.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data gathering

For the chlor-alkali process, data was obtained from García-Herrero *et al* (2017) and Brinkman *et al* (2014). These sources indicate the mass flows and their conditions from the raw materials extraction to final products (NaOH 50 % wt. solution, Cl₂ gas and H₂ gas), along with the fuels and electricity consumption, from which the exergy flows can be calculated. From the different cases, the raw material selected for the analysis was rock salt and the electrolysis technology was membrane cell, because it is most used process worldwide (Millet, 2013).

The chosen process for the sulphuric acid production was the contact process, in particular, a double-contact double-absorption (DC-DA) plant. The mass and energy flows were obtained from an Aspen Hysys® plant example, Kotas (1987), Szargut (1988) and the Ecoinvent database (ecoinvent Association, 2025). The production of sulphur from oil refinery was considered.

The data for exergy cost of electricity was obtained from Torrubia *et al* (2024), separated by source, for two different scenarios: the IEA Net-Zero (NZE) and the Stated Policies Scenario (STEPS). The exergy cost of fossil fuels was calculated from their projected EROI, which was taken from the same source and three others (Font de Mora *et al.*, 2012; Hall *et al.*, 2014; Valero & Valero, 2012). The exergy of the materials flows was obtained using the exergy calculator tool from HSC Chemistry™ Software.

2.2 Processes models

Figure 1 shows the model of the plant and the material and energy flows for the chlor-alkali process. The base unit for this process is 1 ton of Cl₂ product, 1.128 ton of NaOH and 28.5 kg of H₂, which is what is stoichiometrically obtained in the electrolyzer, and hence, is referred to as electrochemical unit (ECU).

Figure 1: Scheme of the chlor-alkali process including material and energy flows

Table 1 summarizes the exergies of the process.

Table 1: Page margins for manuscripts

Flow	Exergy (MJ)
1	490
2	244
3	490
4	0
5	30.8

6	0
7	432
8	9.4
9	1787
10	1230
11	3364
12	38.3
13	28.6
14	1739
15	712
16	1192
17	611
18	126

Figure 2 shows a scheme of the contact process for sulphuric acid production.

Figure 2. Scheme of the DC-DA contact process

As it is possible to see, the process is almost entirely self-supported by the high exergy of elemental sulphur. The electricity consumption is negligible, as it is only used in air blowers and liquid pumps.

2.3 Thermo-economic Analysis

Thermo-economic analysis was carried out using Software TaesLab. This allowed us to obtain exergy cost of each flow based on its completely physical allocation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Direct exergy costs of the chlor-alkali process

Figure 3 shows the direct exergy costs of the three products of the chlor-alkali process and their unitary direct exergy costs (MJ). Hydrogen, due to its extremely high chemical exergy is responsible for almost a half of the exergy cost of the process, despite being less than 3 % of the total products mass. In contrast with conventional LCAs, which allocate the energy consumption to the products by mass or economic value, this methodology emphasizes that most of the energy spent in the process is transformed into hydrogen. If used for LCA, these values could provide a physically-based allocation for consumptions and impacts, which is much more objective than the aforementioned mass or economic value criteria. Consequently, the direct exergy cost per ton of hydrogen is two orders of magnitude greater than for the two other products: 2860 MJ/ton for chlorine, 2370 MJ/ton for sodium hydroxide and 188000 MJ/ton for hydrogen. If hydrogen production is not a priority, a technology like ODC could be considered, which would allow, at least in theory, for important energy savings. The unitary exergy costs, on the other hand, are similar for the three products, as they all are produced in the electrolyzer. The difference in values is a consequence of the use of sulphuric acid to dry the chlorine and steam to concentrate the sodium hydroxide. It must be noted that the unitary cost of hydrogen is similar to what is reported in literature (Lima et al., 2025), which is a sign that the process is efficient for hydrogen production.

Figure 3. Direct and unitary exergy costs of the chlor-alkali process for 1 ECU.

3.2 Evolution of generalized exergy costs of chlor-alkali and contact processes

The thermoeconomic analysis in software TaesLab allowed to modify the parameter for the exergy costs of both fossil and electric energy in the processes. **Figure 4** shows the generalized exergy costs for one ECU of the chlor-alkali process and for 1 ton of sulphuric acid. As the main source of exergy for this process is electricity, it is highly susceptible to variations in the composition of the electrical grid. In the STEPS scenario, the total exergy costs decrease around 30 % for the three products, as the exergy required for the production of electricity decreases due to the lower exergy costs of the renewable energies.

Figure 4. Generalized exergy costs for one ECU of the chlor-alkali process and 1 ton of H₂SO₄ under NZE and STEPS scenarios.

In the NZE scenario, a sharp decrease of the generalized exergy costs can be observed. The fast transition of the grid towards renewable energy impacts deeply on the exergy costs. The steepest change is observed through the first ten years, and by the year 2045, the exergy costs diminish 45 % for hydrogen and chlorine 38 % for NaOH, as this process depends on the natural gas for the steam used for concentrating the solution. The exergy cost of sulphuric acid is almost constant in time – under both

scenarios – as its production process consumes a negligible amount of electricity and is driven mainly by the own chemical exergy of sulphur. In fact, its generalized exergy cost slightly increases due to the shrinking of EROI of fossil fuels in the future.

The aforementioned effects are even more notorious when the fossil exergy costs are analyzed (**Figure 5**). In the NZE scenario, the fossil exergy cost goes down to almost zero – around 10 % of the initial value – for chlorine and hydrogen by 2045. For NaOH, this property stabilizes and reaches a plateau at 25 % of the initial value, being even higher than the fossil cost of hydrogen. As the cause of the higher fossil cost is the steam used to concentrate the sodium hydroxide solution (which is produced using natural gas), a mitigation measure could be the use of heat pumps. In the case of sulphuric acid, as the fossil fuels are used as a source of sulphur and not for electricity, fossil costs remain relatively unchanged. It must be noted, however, that the projected reduction in fossil fuels under the NZE scenario will require new sources of sulphur to be exploited, which might mean higher exergy costs and fossil exergy costs.

Figure 5. Generalized exergy costs for one ECU of the chlor-alkali process and 1 ton of H_2SO_4 under NZE and STEPS scenarios.

3.3 Projection of global exergy consumption for sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide production

Using the generalized exergy costs calculated for sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide and the projection in demand growth, the world exergy consumption for the production of both chemicals was calculated. A 2.7 % compound annual growth rate (CAGR) was assumed for sulphuric acid (Transparency Market Research Inc., 2022), of which an important part is driven by use in metallurgical industry (Grand View Research, 2023). This is consistent with the increase in metals demand due to the energy transition. Regarding sodium hydroxide, the assumed CAGR was 1.4 %. As shown in **Figure 6**, the total exergies consumed to produce each of the reagents are in the same order of magnitude. NaOH production fossil exergy consumption only decreases under NZE scenario. Under STEPS conditions, the reduction in exergy cost is offset by the growth in NaOH demand. Even in the NZE scenario, the fossil exergy consumption for NaOH production starts slowly growing after 2040. This fact highlights both the advantages and the challenges of the energy transition, as a greater manufacture and recycling required by technologies like renewable energies and electric vehicles will require larger consumption and production of reagents like sodium hydroxide. The fossil exergy consumption in H_2SO_4 production grows steadily and rapidly from a value 60 % lower than that of NaOH and surpasses the projection of NaOH under NZE scenario in year 2036. This growth is mainly caused by the increase in demand rather than by the shrinking in fossil fuels EROI.

Figure 6. Projection of annual fossil exergy consumption for sodium hydroxide and sulphuric acid production (worldwide)

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of the present work are:

- Thermo-economic analysis can be used in tandem with life cycle inventory data to obtain the generalized exergy costs for important chemicals.
- The exergy cost of NaOH is highly dependent on electricity grid, as more than 90 % of all the exergy provided to the chlor-alkali process – from the raw materials extraction – is spent in the electrolyzer. Because of the same reason, this process is highly sensitive to the composition of the electric grid. Under the NZE scenario, the exergy costs of chlorine and hydrogen will drop almost 40 %, and the exergy cost of sodium hydroxide around 30 %.
- In opposition to traditional methods, thermo-economic analysis provides a physically-based criterion for allocation. This methodology indicates that almost half of the useful energy provided in the entire process ends up stored as hydrogen, even though it represents less than 3 % of the total mass of products.
- The sulphuric acid production process is thermodynamically driven by the exergy of sulphur, what makes it difficult to find strategies to improve the exergy efficiency. Because of this, the impact of energy transition on the exergy costs – global and fossil – of sulphuric acid is negligible.
- The increase in demand for chemicals in the next years will have deep impacts in the fossil exergy spent worldwide to obtain the two analyzed chemicals. Under optimistic assumptions (NZE), the consumption of fossil exergy for NaOH production will reach a minimum around 2040, and assuming more certain scenarios (STEPS), it will barely go down.

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